

The 9th Seminar on
Numerical Analysis and Its Applications
9-11 May 2022, University of Guilan, Rasht, Iran

PRICING OF EUROPEAN OPTION USING THREE TYPES OF B-SPLINE FUNCTIONS

FARSHID NOURIAN, MEHRDAD LAKESTANI, SEDIGHEH SABERMAHANI,
AND YADOLLAH ORDOKHANI

ABSTRACT. In this paper, we present a numerical method for pricing European options. This approximation method is based on the characteristic function and family of B-Spline function (including: Linear, Quadratic and Cubic B-Spline).

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the most important issues in quantitative finance is pricing options using numerical methods that include numerical solution of PDE, numerical integration and the Monte Carlo method. There are various techniques for numerical integration, such as the Cos method[1], the Wavelet method[3] and the SWIFT method[2].

2. OPTION VALUATION

Here we consider this risk-neutral option valuation formula[2]

$$\begin{aligned}v(x, t) &= \exp(-r(T - t))E^Q [v(y, T) | x] \\ &= \exp(-r(T - t)) \int_R v(y, T) f(y | x) dy,\end{aligned}$$

where v denotes the option value, T is the maturity time, t is the initial date, E^Q is the expectation operator under the risk-neutral measure Q , x and y are state variables

Keywords: Option pricing, B-Spline function, Characteristic function, Collocation method .

AMS Mathematical Subject Classification [2010]: 91B25, 41A15, 74G15 .

at time t and T , respectively, $f(y|x)$ is the probability density of y given x , and r is the deterministic risk-neutral interest rate. The density function f is unknown, while the characteristic function is available for different asset price dynamics, which is the Fourier transform of f .

The variables x and y are also defined as follows

$$x = \ln\left(\frac{S_t}{K}\right) \quad y = \ln\left(\frac{S_T}{K}\right)$$

with S_t the underlying price at time t and K the strike price. Also, the pay-off for European option is obtained from the following equation

$$v(y, T) = [\alpha \cdot K(\exp(y) - 1)]^+,$$

$$\alpha = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{call,} \\ -1, & \text{put.} \end{cases}$$

3. B-SPLINE AND CHARACTERISTIC FUNCTION

Definition 3.1. The s th order of the B-Spline function is defined as follows[3]

$$N_s(x) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} N_{s-1}(x-t)N_0(t)dt = \int_0^1 N_{s-1}(x-t)dt, \quad s \geq 1,$$

where,

$$N_0(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & x \in [0, 1), \\ 0, & \text{o.w.} \end{cases}$$

Definition 3.2. The characteristic function, $g_X(\omega)$ for $\omega \in R$ of the random variable X , is the Fourier-Stieltjes transform of the cumulative distribution function $F_X(x)$, i.e.,

$$(3.1) \quad g_X(\omega) := E[e^{i\omega X}] = \int_R e^{i\omega x} dF_X(x) = \int_R e^{i\omega x} f_X(x) dx.$$

4. NUMERICAL APPROXIMATION

According to the definition of the characteristic function (3.1) for a specific random variable with the density function f , we have

$$g(\omega) = \int_R e^{i\omega x} f(x) dx.$$

For fixed J , a function $f \in L^2[a, b]$ can be approximated using B-Spline functions as

$$(4.1) \quad f(x) \approx f_P(x) = \sum_k c_{J,k} \varphi_{J,k}(x) = C^T \Phi(x),$$

where $\varphi_{J,k}$ s are B-Spline bases, and C and Φ are vectors which their entries are $c_{J,k}$ s and $\varphi_{J,k}$ s, respectively.

Since $f(x)$ rapidly decays to zero as $x \rightarrow \pm\infty$, we truncate the infinite integration range to $[a, b] \subset R$, without losing significant accuracy,

$$g(\omega) = \int_R e^{i\omega x} f(x) dx \simeq \int_a^b e^{i\omega x} f(x) dx.$$

Using relation (4.1) we get

$$g(\omega) = C^T \int_R e^{i\omega x} \Phi(x) dx \simeq C^T \int_a^b e^{i\omega x} \Phi(x) dx.$$

Assume

$$\Psi(\omega) = \int_a^b e^{i\omega x} \Phi(x) dx,$$

so we get

$$(4.2) \quad g(\omega) = c^T \Psi(\omega).$$

Using a suitable collocation method we change the equation (4.2) to a system of Algebraic equation, which can be solve to find the vector C . So the unknown function f , can be found using relation (4.1).

5. NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

Assume that asset price dynamics follow the GBM(Geometric Brownian Motion) process, where the characteristic function is as[3]

$$g_{GBM}(\omega) = \exp(-i\omega x - iw(r - q - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2)(T - t) - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2\omega^2(T - t)).$$

Let

$$(5.1) \quad S_0 = 100, \quad r = 0.1, \quad q = 0, \quad T = 0.1, \quad \sigma = 0.25,$$

we solve the problem for two strike price $K = 80$ and $K = 120$.

Table 1 and 2 show the absolute errors for different values of j and different orders of B-Spline functions.

TABLE 1. The absolute errors for different values of j and different orders of B-Spline functions, with parameters as in (5.1); $K = 80$; reference val.= 20.799226309

-	$j = 4$	$j = 5$
Linear B-Spline	1.1×10^{-3}	3.7×10^{-6}
Quadratic B-Spline	2.9×10^{-3}	8.2×10^{-7}
Cubic B-Spline	3.9×10^{-4}	3.09×10^{-7}

TABLE 2. The absolute errors for different values of j and different orders of B-Spline functions, with parameters as in (5.1); $K = 120$; reference val.= 0.044577814

-	$j = 4$	$j = 5$
Linear B-Spline	6.7×10^{-4}	2.5×10^{-5}
Quadratic B-Spline	2.8×10^{-5}	2.4×10^{-6}
Cubic B-Spline	1.4×10^{-5}	2.5×10^{-7}

REFERENCES

- [1] Fang, Fang and Oosterlee, Cornelis W. ; A Novel Pricing Method for European Options Based on Fourier-Cosine Series Expansions. *SIAM J. SCI. COMPUT.* 31 (2008), no. 2, 826-848.
- [2] Ortiz-Gracia, Luis and Oosterlee, Cornelis W. ; A Highly Efficient Shannon Wavelet Inverse Fourier Technique for Pricing European Options. *SIAM J. SCI. COMPUT.* 38 (2016), no. 1, B118-B143.
- [3] Ortiz-Gracia, Luis and Oosterlee, Cornelis W. ; Robust Pricing of European Options with Wavelets and the Characteristic Function. *SIAM J. SCI. COMPUT.* 35 (2013), no. 5, B1055-B1084.

DEPARTMENT OF APPLIED MATHEMATICS, FACULTY OF MATHEMATICS, STATISTICS AND COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF TABRIZ, TABRIZ, IRAN

E-mail address: f.nourian@tabrizu.ac.ir

DEPARTMENT OF APPLIED MATHEMATICS, FACULTY OF MATHEMATICS, STATISTICS AND COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF TABRIZ, TABRIZ, IRAN

E-mail address: lakestani@tabrizu.ac.ir

DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS, FACULTY OF MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES, ALZAHRA UNIVERSITY, TEHRAN, IRAN

E-mail address: s.saber@alzahra.ac.ir

DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS, FACULTY OF MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES, ALZAHRA UNIVERSITY, TEHRAN, IRAN

E-mail address: ordokhani@alzahra.ac.ir